

Summary of the study's material

What do we know about implementing ethical principles
in the context of Artificial Intelligence?
A Systematic Literature Review

September 7, 2024

1. Data extracted from the papers
2. Table of automated search strings
3. Primary studies table
4. Data form table
5. Table of studies used in RQ2
6. Table of studies used in RQ3
7. Table of ethical AI principles found in literature